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The Importance of Historical Turkish Marches in the Path of World Culture and Economic Development

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***Abstract:** The development of statehood issues, economic, political, ecological and cultural strategies of turkish people, and its application in peripheral areas, especially in the Eurasian zone, are briefly examined in this article. The main aim is not also learning the historical role and place of the Silk Road as a symbol of intercultural dialogue, ethnic integration, influencing to the cultural and economic context, but also the perspectives of the COP 29 project.*

***Key words:** history, Turkish marches, Azerbaijan, COP 29, culture.*

Introduction

In this article, the development of statehood issues, economic, political, ecological and cultural strategies of the Turks, and its application in peripheral areas, especially in the Eurasian zone, are briefly examined. The main goal is to study the historical role and place of the Silk Road as a symbol of intercultural dialogue, ethnic integration, deepening of the cultural and economic context, as well as the perspectives of the COP 29 project. The modern challenge as the initiator of the historical, cultural and geographical potential of renewing the energy problems in the conditions of globalization, the joint role of the Turkish peoples in this matter is investigated.

The conducted historical studies show that the Silk Road is the most important historical communication route between the ancient civilizations of the world, and it is a factor in the adaptation of human diversity in the formation of different civilizations in history. Throughout history, peoples and tribes have exchanged material goods and their cultural structures over this longest potential route, resulting in the largest and most extensive programs of cultural diffusion. The road has developed as a result of trade-economic interaction and as a critical necessity for the coexistence of different peoples in the process of cultural relations over the centuries. According to the famous Kazakh philosopher Nurjanov, the great Silk Road was an experience of world globalization.

The role of Turkish civilization as one of the oldest means of cultural communication, political and economic development is undeniable. The historical, cultural and geographical potential of globalization and its renewal has been strengthened and raised on this foundation.

Road construction is a fact in the history of several thousand years. Europe and Asia are magnificent regions with very interesting nature, such as the majestic mountains of the Caucasus, the Alps, the Gobi and Indian deserts, countless rivers and other natural beauties. Although the villages and cities in the area are far from each other, the administrative rules and determination of the Turkic people successfully solved all trade and travel problems.

The Silk Road was the origin of many of the richest cities built around this strategic and commercial route. With the boom of this road, huge obstacles were swamped and rotted. Civilizations in the global network of roads absorbed many cultural elements from other tribes with whom present-day indigenous Turkic elements had trade relations along the route. The road connecting the Mediterranean Sea from the southern part of the Caspian Sea to China was not only the road of merchants, but also the only way for the powers of states to exchange messages of peace and friendship between neighbors.

The re-actualization of the Great Silk Road in modern international life is a historical regularity of the world. This means that the role of the Turkic world, returning to the Great Politics, in the political, economic and cultural life of modern Eurasia has been realized again, with greater force. "Today, the Turks, who are the historical guardians of the Great Silk Road, are in the mission of its founders. Independent Turkic states: Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus and other Turkic peoples confirm the concept of Turkic world. The world of Turkic peoples and their role in history is priceless. Thus, the contributions of Turkish history to world history, culture, science, i.e. historical monuments, world-famous personalities, and patriotic personalities are justified"(1).

The Main Part

Historically and today, scientists and thinkers of the Turkic world have proven themselves all over the world with their works and historical discoveries in the field of literature and exact sciences. Among them is Selçuk Bayraktar, who works in the field of military engineering. The conducted historical studies show that the Silk Road is the most important historical communication route between the ancient civilizations of the world, and it is a factor in the adaptation of human diversity in the formation of different civilizations in history. How important is the historical, cultural and geographical potential of globalization and its renewal in studying the role and place of the Silk Road, intercultural dialogue, integration of ethnicities, the deepening of the cultural and economic context, the texts of the ancient Turks from the period of the Turkish Khanate, classical examples from the Golden Age, as well as various The works of medieval literary scholars such as Nizami Ganjavi, Al-Biruni, Nasiruddin Tusi, Ulug Bey, and Piri Reis played a major role in the researches of Muslim scholars: philosophers, cultural scholars, and monographs.

Throughout history, peoples and tribes have exchanged material goods over their cultural structures in this longest potential way, resulting in the largest and most extensive programs of cultural diffusion. The road has developed as a result of trade-economic interaction and as a critical necessity for the coexistence of different peoples in the process of cultural relations over the centuries. The center of attention on the level of the single spirituality of sciences and cultures emerged as a historical model and a meaningful requirement of mutual cultural coexistence in the intellectual space of the Silk Road.

However, humanity has reached such a time that now the Turkish states must demonstrate stronger solidarity than before in order to properly secure their interests, and this is a historical necessity. Because international law, which has already been eroded, today just plays the role of a pressure tool in the hands of power centers and does not protect the interests of other states in any case. As a result, global cataclysms have become one of the geopolitical realities of the system of international relations. International law is not able to protect peace and stability in the world from cataclysms. The Turkish states, which have confidently advanced towards new strategic goals and become a rising power center in world politics, and whose international influence and geopolitical influence are increasing, are also facing similar challenges. Therefore, the unity of the Turkic world is more important against the background of the mentioned global problems and cataclysms.

The decision to hold COP29 in Azerbaijan is an unequivocal expression of great trust and respect for our country. We must not forget that, as President Ilham Aliyev stated in the meeting held on December 15, 2023, we earned this respect with our actions, work, and politics. "Our independent policy, our principled position, our commitment to international law, our loyalty and at the same time the restoration of sovereignty in the country's territory have increased the respect for us." In particular, the unanimous decision to hold COP29 in Baku only 2 and a half months after the local anti-terrorist measures is a serious victory for Baku against the background of inadequate and unfair approaches of a number of Western subjects and appreciation of our rightful position"(2).

We believe that Azerbaijan's hosting of the COP will be a presentation of itself as a global power that understands its international responsibility:

"On the other hand, seeing its future not in the oil and gas sphere, but in alternative energy, defining itself as a "clean environment and green growth country" as one of the five national priorities, and setting very bold targets for the drastic reduction of carbon dioxide emissions with the Kyoto protocol. Azerbaijan is actually the most sensitive member of the UN Framework Convention on climate change. Against the background of all this, the statements of some biased pseudo-politician cannot affect the essence of the already adopted decision Hosting COP 29 will also be a presentation of Azerbaijan as a global power that is committed to the rule of international law, believes in justice and understands its international responsibility in the new reality"(3).

The Turkish states, which have confidently advanced towards new strategic goals and become a rising power center in world politics, and whose international influence and geopolitical influence are increasing, are also facing similar challenges. Therefore, the unity of the Turkic world is more important against the background of the mentioned global problems and cataclysms. And TDT plays the role of a bridge on the way to exit these global processes successfully and quickly and to minimize losses. The relations of the Turkish states represented in this organization, based on the principles of friendship and brotherhood, mutual understanding, equal partnership and multifaceted cooperation, in the conditions of close solidarity, are a very important factor that serves stability, security and development both at the national and regional levels, and at the global level. The targeted initiatives of the heads of state of TDT to constantly develop, strengthen and deepen Turkish integration are also commendable.

The strategic document of TDT begins with this sentence: "We are living in an era that makes it important to have a strategic vision to recognize and handle the rapid changes on a global scale and their effects on us" (1) Yes, the events and processes experienced in the world are international, regional and intercontinental. created the need to have a strategic vision.

These issues were discussed in detail in three plenary sessions organized within the framework of the international conference held in Shusha on the topics “Organization of Turkish States: regional contribution to global security”, “Unity of common values and modernity: party diplomacy as a new dialogue platform” and “Turkish World-2040: a conceptual vision of the future” were made, proposals, initiatives were voiced. The voiced opinions intersected in such a common denominator that the main way for the Turkish states to overcome the global cataclysms together and come out strong from this process is to further deepen the cooperation within the framework of TDT.

Thus, the mission carried by the Silk Road historically falls on Azerbaijan as a Turkic state. Both restoring the modern role of the Silk Road and connecting the Asian continent with Europe more cost-effectively and comfortably, and successfully implementing the COP 29 project to stabilize the planet's energy environment, lead a great strategy to ensure a peaceful life on Earth, organize and regulate these things with dignity brings honor to our country.

The Result

In conclusion, let's note that the TAP, TANAP and Zangezur projects, as well as COP 29, will provide new platforms for regional cooperation and security, strengthening legal, economic, cultural relations and mutual understanding between the participating countries. As the main segment of the Southern Gas Corridor, TANAP will deliver gas produced from the Shahdeniz-2 gas-condensate field in the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea to European consumers. TANAP connects to Europe, while TAP connects to Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey, and then continues to cover Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia, Albania, Serbia and Bosnia-Herzegovina. We hope that the Great Silk Road will be fully restored and all mankind will benefit from it.

Thus, in this article, we tried to evaluate the joint services of the Turkish states in two historical projects, the Great Silk Road and COP29, and in our opinion, we achieved our scientific goal.

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